

Spontaneous Evolution from Electron-Only to Standard Reconnection in a Force-Free Current Sheet

Jincai Ren¹, San Lu^{2,3,4}, Rony Keppens¹

¹Centre for mathematical Plasma Astrophysics, Department of Mathematics, KU Leuven, Celestijnenlaan 200B, Leuven, Belgium

²CAS Center for Excellence in Comparative Planetology, CAS Key Lab of Geospace Environment, School of Earth and Space Sciences, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei, Anhui, China

³Deep Space Exploration Laboratory, Hefei, Anhui, China

⁴Collaborative Innovation Center of Astronautical Science and Technology, Harbin, China

Key Points:

- Spontaneous temporal evolution from electron-only to standard reconnection is studied via PIC simulations in the presence of the guide field
- The in-plane electric field is found to be the main contributor to ion acceleration during the evolution
- This temporal evolution from electron-only to standard reconnection is blocked when the ion gyroradius is comparable to the box size

Corresponding author: Jincai Ren, jincairen.physics@gmail.com

Corresponding author: San Lu, lusan@ustc.edu.cn

Abstract

Electron-only reconnection is a novel reconnection regime observed recently in the turbulent magnetosheath and magnetotail, related to energy conversion and large-scale reconnection events. However, the relationship between this novel regime and standard kinetic reconnection is still not fully understood. In this paper, we investigate the spontaneous evolution from electron-only to standard reconnection in a force-free current sheet under guide fields using 2.5-dimensional particle-in-cell (PIC) simulations. Our results reveal that reconnection occurs within the electron-only regime initially, where ion outflow jets and ion heating are absent. This absence is attributed to the spatial limitations of the downstream region, which restricts the influence of electric forces, thereby preventing significant ion acceleration. Consequently, the negligible ion outflow velocities result in minimal work done by the pressure gradient term, and the contribution of ion enthalpy flux remains insignificant, thereby leading to the lack of ion heating during this phase. As reconnection proceeds, the available space for ion acceleration increases, allowing for both ion heating and the development of ion outflow jets, which ultimately results in a temporal evolution to the standard kinetic reconnection regime. We further examine the effect of ion temperature on this temporal evolution and discover that high ion temperature inhibits this temporal evolution from electron-only to standard reconnection, confining reconnection to the electron-only regime throughout the simulation even though the simulation domain is large. This work provides insights into the role of electron-only reconnection in the magnetosheath.

1 Introduction

Magnetic reconnection is a fundamental process in which magnetic field lines break and reconnect, resulting in changes to the topology of magnetic fields (Biskamp, 2000; Birn & Priest, 2007; Yamada et al., 2010; Q. Lu et al., 2023). During this process, magnetic energy is converted into kinetic and thermal energy of plasma, and it is thought to be the underlying mechanism of many phenomena in nature, including solar flares, coronal mass ejections (CMEs), geomagnetic storms and substorms, as well as sawtooth crashes in fusion devices (Biskamp, 2000; Yamada et al., 2010; Goedbloed et al., 2019; Hesse & Cassak, 2020). Usually, both ions and electrons are involved in the magnetic reconnection process, resulting in outflow jets for both species in the downstream regions (Hesse & Cassak, 2020). Consequently, this process is often referred to as ‘standard reconnection’, and significant progress has been made in understanding this regime over the past decades (Hesse & Cassak, 2020; Ji et al., 2023; Q. Lu et al., 2023). This standard reconnection regime where both ions and electrons have Alfvénic outflow jets can also be investigated in a single fluid magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) description, although the MHD view lacks crucial kinetic effects and is therefore limited in its applicability to collisionless plasmas.

More recently, a novel regime called ‘electron-only reconnection’ has been identified in the turbulent magnetosheath (Phan et al., 2018; Stawarz et al., 2019; Payne et al., 2025), magnetotail (S. Lu, Wang, et al., 2020; R. Wang et al., 2020; Hubbert et al., 2021, 2022; S. Lu et al., 2022), bow shock (Gingell et al., 2019), and magnetopause (P. Pyakurel et al., 2025). Differently from standard reconnection, this regime is characterized by the absence of ion outflow jets, while super-Alfvénic electron outflow jets are still present (Phan et al., 2018; Califano et al., 2020; Arrò et al., 2020; Granier et al., 2024; Fan et al., 2025). The degree of ion coupling in electron-only reconnection is either lacking or significantly reduced compared to standard reconnection (Sharma Pyakurel et al., 2019; Yi et al., 2022). Furthermore, ion heating is negligible, whereas electron heating is prominent in this regime (S. Lu, Angelopoulos, Artemyev, Pritchett, et al., 2020). However, the relationship between electron-only reconnection and standard reconnection is still not fully understood. Clearly, such electron-only reconnection necessitates at least a two-fluid ion-electron de-

68 scription, while collisionless kinetic effects can only be understood using full particle-in-
69 cell (PIC) approaches. Here, we focus on PIC strategies.

70 Previous simulation studies have provided insights into this relationship, suggest-
71 ing that the ratio between the simulation box size and the ion characteristic length scale
72 plays a critical role in distinguishing these two regimes (Sharma Pyakurel et al., 2019;
73 Guan et al., 2023). For example, Guan et al. (2023) demonstrated that the ratio between
74 the simulation box size L and the ion cyclotron radius ρ_i determines the degree of ion
75 coupling in guide-field reconnection. By systematically varying the ratio L/ρ_i while keep-
76 ing the box size relatively small, they found that electron-only reconnection is observed
77 when L is comparable to ρ_i ($L \sim \rho_i$). In contrast, the reconnection shifts to the con-
78 ventional ion-coupled regime once L/ρ_i becomes comparable to several tens. On the other
79 hand, electron-only reconnection has been found to act as a transitional phase between
80 a quiet current sheet and standard reconnection in the magnetotail (S. Lu, Angelopou-
81 los, Artemyev, Pritchett, et al., 2020; Hubbert et al., 2021, 2022). Subsequent PIC sim-
82 ulation results provide a consistent picture of this transitional role of electron-only re-
83 connection under strong external drivers, where the current sheet thins first and then
84 reconnection initiates (S. Lu et al., 2022). More recently, Guan et al. (2025) investigated
85 the temporal evolution from electron-only reconnection to standard reconnection and an-
86 alyzed the roles of particles and magnetic field pileup. Nevertheless, whether this tem-
87 poral evolution occurs during spontaneous reconnection in the presence of guide fields
88 remains unresolved. It is also an open question how this temporal evolution takes place
89 in this case (in this work, we refer to regime identification across different simulations
90 as a “transition”, as used in previous parameter-scan studies (Sharma Pyakurel et al.,
91 2019; Guan et al., 2023), whereas we refer to the continuous development within a sin-
92 gular simulation as a “temporal evolution”).

93 Particles are both accelerated and heated during reconnection, a topic that has been
94 extensively studied, particularly in the context of standard reconnection (Shay et al., 2014;
95 Dahlin et al., 2014; Yamada et al., 2015; Pucci et al., 2018; Shu et al., 2021; Yi et al.,
96 2020). In standard reconnection, electrons are accelerated in the outflow direction, with
97 their maximum velocity reaching up to the electron Alfvén speed V_{Ae} within the elec-
98 tron diffusion region (EDR), as indicated by scaling analyses (Hesse et al., 2009). Ions,
99 on the other hand, are accelerated within the ion diffusion region (IDR), and both species
100 contribute to the formation of outflow jets at the boundary of the IDR with speeds on
101 the order of the Alfvén speed V_A , as calculated using the upstream asymptotic magnetic
102 field component (Chang et al., 2024). The ion dynamics in electron-only reconnection
103 were studied by Guan et al. (2024), and they found that the in-plane electric field de-
104 celerates the outflowing electrons while accelerating ions, thereby explaining why the peak
105 electron outflow velocity is less than the electron Alfvén speed V_{Ae} . Roy et al. (2024)
106 investigated energy dissipation in both electron-only and standard reconnection regimes
107 through a combination of observational data and 2.5-dimensional PIC simulations. Yi
108 et al. (2022) studied electron-only reconnection during island coalescence in anti-parallel
109 reconnection and found that the temporal scale of the merging process plays a key role
110 in determining the degree of ion coupling. Ren et al. (2025) examined electron heating
111 in electron-only reconnection with strong guide fields through PIC simulations within
112 a small simulation box, demonstrating that the electron temperature anisotropy and elec-
113 tron velocity distribution functions are significantly influenced by the guide field inten-
114 sity. However, the behavior of ion dynamics and the mechanisms of ion heating during
115 the temporal evolution from electron-only to standard reconnection, particularly for a
116 force-free current sheet in the presence of guide fields, are yet to be fully elucidated.

117 In this work, we investigate the development of reconnection through 2.5-dimensional
118 PIC simulations with a long force-free current sheet, focusing on the temporal evolution
119 from electron-only reconnection to standard reconnection as well as the role of ion tem-
120 perature in influencing this evolution. The ion outflow velocity has been widely used as

121 a criterion to distinguish between these two reconnection regimes (Sharma Pyakurel et
 122 al., 2019; Guan et al., 2023; Ren et al., 2025; Guan et al., 2024, 2025). Additionally, S. Lu
 123 et al. (2022) proposed that ion temperature remains unchanged during electron-only re-
 124 connection, whereas it exhibits a significant increase in standard reconnection. In this
 125 study, we adopt the combination of these two conditions: reconnection is classified as ‘electron-
 126 only’ when the ion temperature remains constant and ion outflow jets are either absent
 127 or negligible; conversely, reconnection is identified as standard when the ion tempera-
 128 ture increases prominently and ion outflow jets are evident.

129 The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 describes the initial equilibrium
 130 and simulation setup. The simulation results, including the reconnection evolution, evo-
 131 lution mechanisms analyses, and the influence of ion temperature, are presented in Sec-
 132 tion 3. Conclusions and discussions are given in Section 4.

133 2 Simulation Setup

134 We employ 2.5-dimensional simulations using a fully kinetic semi-implicit PIC code
 135 ECsim (Lapenta, 2017). The simulations are initialized with a force-free equilibrium ,
 136 which has been widely adopted in recent simulation studies of electron-only reconec-
 137 tion (P. Pyakurel et al., 2021; Guan et al., 2023; P. S. Pyakurel et al., 2023; Ren et al.,
 138 2025; Fan et al., 2025) and has also been observed in various space plasma environments,
 139 including in the magnetotail (Kivelson & Khurana, 1995; Vasko et al., 2014; Zelenyi et
 140 al., 2016), in the magnetopause (Panov et al., 2011), and in the solar corona (Wiegelmann
 141 & Sakurai, 2021). In our simulations, x is the direction along the in-plane magnetic field,
 142 y is the direction vertical to the current sheet and z is the out-of-plane direction. The
 143 x component of the initial magnetic field profile takes the following form

$$B_x(y) = B_{x0} \left[\tanh\left(\frac{y - y_1}{\delta_1}\right) - \tanh\left(\frac{y - y_2}{\delta_2}\right) - 1 \right], \quad (1)$$

144 such that we actually have two horizontal current layers in our simulation domain, situ-
 145 ated at y_1 and y_2 . The out-of-plane magnetic field B_z is given by

$$B_z(y) = [B_g^2 + B_{x0}^2 - B_x^2(y)]^{1/2}, \quad (2)$$

146 with B_g representing the asymptotic guide field far from the current sheet. Here y_1 and
 147 y_2 are the positions of the two current sheets, with $y_1 = L_y/4$ and $y_2 = 3L_y/4$. δ_1 and
 148 δ_2 are the thicknesses of the two current sheets at $y = y_1$ and $y = y_2$, respectively.
 149 The two current sheets have different thicknesses, which are $\delta_1 = 0.075d_i$ (the upper
 150 sheet, here d_i is ion inertial length) and $\delta_2 = 0.15d_i$ (the lower sheet), respectively. The
 151 mass ratio is $m_i/m_e = 100$. In our simulations, the magnetic field B is normalized to
 152 $B_{\text{norm}} = m_i\omega_{pi}/e$, where $\omega_{pi} = \sqrt{n_0e^2/\varepsilon_0m_i}$ is the ion plasma frequency, and e and
 153 m_i are the ion charge and mass, respectively. In this normalization, the ratio of the elec-
 154 tron plasma frequency to the electron cyclotron frequency is $\omega_{pe}/\omega_{ce} = 8.84$, where $\omega_{pe} =$
 155 $\sqrt{n_0e^2/\varepsilon_0m_e}$ and $\omega_{ce} = eB/m_e$. The strength of the asymptotic in-plane magnetic
 156 field strength and the guide field are both 0.008. The initial current is calculated from
 157 Ampère’s law (without displacement current) and all currents are carried by electrons.
 158 This choice is supported by the fact that electron-dominated current sheets are commonly
 159 observed in space plasmas. For instance, such configurations have been reported in the
 160 Earth’s magnetotail (S. Lu et al., 2019; S. Lu, Angelopoulos, Artemyev, Jia, et al., 2020),
 161 and statistical analyses have shown that, in the most intense current structures at the
 162 dayside magnetopause, the current is predominantly carried by electrons (Man et al., 2021).
 163 Particles are initialized from Maxwellian distributions. The density is uniform for both
 164 species and quasi-neutrality is initially satisfied. The electron β_e (the ratio of the ther-
 165 mal pressure to the magnetic pressure) is 1. We conduct two simulations that differ only
 166 in their ion temperature, corresponding to ion β_i values of 2.56 and 25.0, respectively.
 167 The simulation box size is $L_x \times L_y = 25d_i \times 25d_i$ and it is discretized with $N_x \times N_y =$

168 2000 \times 2000 cells. The total number of particles is 8.2 billion in each simulation. The
 169 time step is $dt = 0.04\omega_{pi}^{-1}$. Both the electron gyroradius and electron cyclotron peri-
 170 ods are resolved with this resolution. Periodic boundary conditions are used in all di-
 171 rections. We do not add perturbations to our simulations and the reconnection is initi-
 172 ated by noise. The evolution of these two current sheets is found to be quite similar
 173 and we choose the lower current sheet to do the analysis below. In practice, having two
 174 current layers in the domain allows for using fully periodic boundaries such that basic
 175 conservation properties apply, essentially resulting in two realizations of the reconnect-
 176 ing layer per simulation. As we vary the thickness parameters $\delta_{1,2}$, the evolution of both
 177 current sheets evolves with a slight phase difference.

178 3 Results

179 In this section, we first present the temporal evolution process from electron-only
 180 reconnection to standard reconnection in our simulations and analyze the underlying mech-
 181 anisms that govern this temporal evolution, specifically focusing on the factors that af-
 182 fect the extent of ion coupling. Subsequently, we investigate the influence of ion temper-
 183 ature on this evolution. Our findings suggest that the temporal evolution from electron-
 184 only to standard reconnection is strongly inhibited when the ion temperature is sufficiently
 185 large. In other words, the reconnection remains in the electron-only regime throughout
 186 the evolution when the ion temperature is high enough, even in a relatively large sim-
 187 ulation box.

188 3.1 Spontaneous evolution from electron-only to standard reconnection

189 The evolution of the reconnected flux and reconnection rate is presented in Fig-
 190 ure 1. The blue curve represents the reconnected flux, calculated as the difference be-
 191 tween the values of the vector potential A_z at the X-point and the O-point along the lower
 192 current sheet. The red curve illustrates the evolution of the reconnection rate, defined
 193 as the time derivative of the reconnected flux. During the early stage ($t < 1000\omega_{pi}^{-1}$),
 194 the reconnection rate is significantly greater than 0.1 and is not steady, similar to the
 195 evolution observed in electron-only reconnection simulations with strong guide fields in
 196 a much smaller simulation box (Ren et al., 2025). Besides, they are also consistent with
 197 the electron-only reconnection events as found in observations (Tian et al., 2025). In the
 198 later stage, particularly for $t > 1500\omega_{pi}^{-1}$, the reconnection rate reaches a steady phase
 199 with a value of approximately 0.1, which is characteristic of standard reconnection (Liu
 200 et al., 2017; Hesse & Cassak, 2020). This indicates that the system has reached a steady-
 201 state reconnection phase corresponding to the standard reconnection regime.

202 We subsequently analyzed the reconnection structure at different times. As men-
 203 tioned earlier, the simulation contains two current sheets with different thicknesses and
 204 their evolution is similar, but the reconnection onset in the lower sheet is later than the
 205 upper one (since it is two times thicker). To better illustrate the evolution of electron
 206 and ion responses, we focused our analysis on the reconnection site located at the bot-
 207 tom right corner of the simulation domain, specifically at the rightmost X-line of the lower
 208 current sheet. By the end of the simulation, the available magnetic flux for reconnection
 209 remains unexhausted, and the magnetic islands along one current sheet have not yet in-
 210 teracted with those of the other sheet. In other words, the two current sheets have no
 211 significant impact on each other, allowing us to rule out the possibility that the results
 212 presented here are influenced by interactions with the other current sheet (as presented
 213 in Appendix Appendix A).

214 The electron velocity along the x direction at four different time snapshots is shown
 215 in Figure 2 (a) to (d). V_{ex} is the electron bulk velocity along the x direction and V_A is
 216 the Alfvén speed, which is calculated using the upstream in-plane asymptotic magnetic
 217 field. The solid lines represent the in-plane magnetic field lines. At $t = 280\omega_{pi}^{-1}$, mag-

Figure 1. Evolution of reconnected flux Ψ and reconnection rate E_r . The reconnection rate E_r is normalized by $V_A B_{x0}$, with V_A representing the inflow Alfvén speed and B_{x0} denoting the in-plane asymptotic magnetic field.

218 netic islands form as shown in Figure 2 (b), which marks the onset of magnetic recon-
 219 nection. A chain of islands is distributed along the current sheet. As reconnection pro-
 220 gresses, the islands merge and elongate along the x direction. Super-Alfvénic electron
 221 outflows are observed on both sides of the X-point at $x = 17.8d_i$. Due to this coales-
 222 cence, the downstream region also extends in the x direction. In Figure 2 (c), the islands
 223 grow to be larger and the electron outflow velocity decreases compared to earlier times.
 224 As seen in Figure 1, the reconnection gradually transitions to a steady standard recon-
 225 nection phase after $t = 1000\omega_{pi}^{-1}$. In Figure 2 (d), the structure corresponds to the fully
 226 developed standard reconnection regime, and the electron outflow velocity has reached
 227 the order of the Alfvén speed.

228 The ion velocity along the x direction (normalized by the upstream Alfvén speed)
 229 at the corresponding four times is shown in Figure 3. In Figure 3 (b), the ion velocity
 230 on both sides of the X-points is not discernible, although the change in magnetic field
 231 line topology indicates the onset of reconnection at this time. The ion velocity on both
 232 sides of the X-point at $x = 17.8d_i$ is less than $0.05V_A$ and there are no discernible ion
 233 outflows for the other two X-points at $x = 14.5d_i$ and $x = 22.0$ in Figure 3 (b). As
 234 the islands merge, the ion flows on both sides of the X-point at $x = 17.8$ turn to be more
 235 prominent, as shown in Figure 3 (c), which means the degree of ion coupling to the re-
 236 connection process increases dramatically. In Figure 3 (c) and (d), the downstream re-
 237 gion becomes elongated and there is more space for ions to be accelerated. As a result,
 238 the ion velocity increases noticeably, indicating greater ion involvement in the recon-
 239 nection process. At the time $t = 2400\omega_{pi}^{-1}$, the ion outflow velocity increases to the order
 240 of $0.3V_A$. The 1-dimensional cuts of the ion velocity $V_{i,x}$, electron velocity $V_{e,x}$, and $(\mathbf{E} \times$
 241 $\mathbf{B})_x$ drift speed along the lower current sheet at $t = 2400\omega_{pi}^{-1}$ is shown in Figure 4. These
 242 profiles show that, far from the diffusion region, the ion outflow velocity closely matches
 243 both the electron velocity and the $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ drift, indicating that ions are re-magnetized
 244 and the system has entered the standard reconnection regime.

245 Ion heating provides another key indicator that differentiates between electron-only
 246 reconnection and standard reconnection. Figure 5 illustrates the temperature variations
 247 for both species at two distinct times. Here $\Delta T_s = (T_s(t = t_1)/T_s(t = 0)) - 1$, where
 248 T is temperature, the subscript 's' denotes species, and t is time. In the left column, elec-
 249 trons exhibit significant heating, while ion temperature shows no discernible change dur-

Figure 2. Evolution of the electron flow velocity along the x direction, normalized by the upstream Alfvén speed, V_{ex}/V_A . The Alfvén speed is calculated using the asymptotic in-plane magnetic field, B_{x0} . Electron outflows are observed following the onset of reconnection. As reconnection progresses, the reconnection region elongates, and the electron outflow velocity gradually decreases. The solid black curves represent the magnetic field lines. All plots share a common colorbar, positioned on the right side of the figure.

Figure 3. Evolution of the ion flow velocity along the x direction, normalized by the upstream Alfvén speed, V_{ix}/V_A . The panels are taken at the same times as those for the electron outflows from Figure 2. The Alfvén speed is calculated using the asymptotic in-plane magnetic field, B_{x0} . Ion outflows are absent or negligible at the early phase of reconnection. As reconnection progresses, the reconnection region elongates, and the ion outflow velocity gradually increases. The solid black curves represent the magnetic field lines. All plots share a common colorbar, positioned on the right side of the figure. The lime boxes in panels (b) and (d) indicate the regions used for spatial integration of the terms in Equation 5 for the first simulation at two different times; the corresponding integration results are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 4. 1-dimensional cuts of the ion velocity $V_{i,x}$, electron velocity $V_{e,x}$, and $(\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B})_x$ drift speed along the lower current sheet at $t = 2400\omega_{pi}^{-1}$ in the first simulation.

Figure 5. The electron (top) and ion (bottom) temperature variations at two times are shown. Here $\Delta T_s = (T_s(t = t_1)/T_s(t = 0)) - 1$. The left column corresponds to the electron-only reconnection regime, while the right is the standard reconnection regime. Figures within the same row share a common colorbar, which is positioned on the right side of the corresponding row.

250 ing the electron-only reconnection phase ($t = 280\omega_{pi}^{-1}$). In contrast, the right column
 251 demonstrates that both electrons and ions undergo heating during the standard recon-
 252 nection stage ($t = 2400\omega_{pi}^{-1}$).

253 3.2 Evolution mechanism

254 A key distinction between electron-only reconnection and standard reconnection
 255 lies in the extent of ion involvement in the reconnection process. Specifically, the pres-
 256 ence and magnitude of ion outflows are critical indicators distinguishing these two regimes.
 257 In electron-only reconnection, both the temporal and spatial scales for ions to respond
 258 to changes in magnetic topology are constrained. Consequently, ion outflow jets are ei-
 259 ther absent or significantly weaker than those in standard reconnection. In contrast, in
 260 standard reconnection, the ion outflow velocity typically reaches the order of the upstream
 261 Alfvén speed (V_A), indicating much stronger ion involvement in the reconnection dynam-
 262 ics.

263 In collisionless magnetic reconnection, the ion momentum equation in the x direc-
 264 tion, in the Newtonian regime, is given by

$$m_i \frac{dV_{ix}}{dt} = eE_x + e(\mathbf{V}_i \times \mathbf{B})_x - \frac{(\nabla \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{P}}_i)_x}{n_i}, \quad (3)$$

265 where m_i is the ion mass, $\frac{dV_{ix}}{dt}$ is the time derivative of the ion velocity in the x direc-
 266 tion, e denotes charge, and E_x represents the electric field in the x direction. The term
 267 $(\mathbf{V}_i \times \mathbf{B})_x$ represents the Lorentz force on ions in the x direction, $(\nabla \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{P}}_i)_x$ is the x -

268 component of the divergence of the ion pressure tensor $\overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{P}}_i$, and n_i is the ion number density.
 269 The first term on the RHS of Eq. 3 represents the acceleration due to the electric
 270 field. The second term is the effect of the Lorentz force in the x -direction and the third
 271 term denotes the influence of the ion pressure tensor. Figure 6 presents profiles of these
 272 three terms at time $t = 280\omega_{pi}^{-1}$ (i.e. the electron-only reconnection phase) and $t = 2400\omega_{pi}^{-1}$
 273 (i.e. the standard reconnection stage). Among them, subplots (a), (c), and (e) are the
 274 profiles of these three terms on the RHS of Eq. 3 at time $t = 280\omega_{pi}^{-1}$. Subplots (b),
 275 (d), and (f) present profiles of these three terms at $t = 2400\omega_{pi}^{-1}$. The electric field in
 276 the outflow direction E_x could be decomposed as follows:

$$E_x = -\frac{1}{en}(J_y B_z - J_z B_y) - \frac{1}{en}(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{P}_e)_x - \frac{m_e}{e} \left(\frac{d\mathbf{v}_e}{dt} \right)_x + \dots \quad (4)$$

277 where the first term corresponds to the Hall electric field, the second to the divergence
 278 of the electron pressure tensor, and the third to the electron inertia. We plot 1-dimensional
 279 cuts of each term on the RHS of equation 4 along the lower current sheet at $t = 2400\omega_{pi}^{-1}$,
 280 plotted alongside the total E_x , as shown in Figure 7. Consistent with previous findings
 281 (Liu et al., 2025), the profiles clearly show that the Hall term dominates over all other
 282 terms by more than an order of magnitude in the outflow region, confirming that it is
 283 the primary driver of ion acceleration in the late-time standard reconnection regime. Con-
 284 sequently, these results suggest that the in-plane Hall electric field force eE_x dominates
 285 ion acceleration during this phase.

286 The Lorentz force term is much smaller than the electric field term at these two
 287 times. The last term (ion pressure tensor term) remains negligible. The elongation of
 288 the reconnection site along the x direction provides more space for ions to be acceler-
 289 ated. As a result, the work done on the ions increases, promoting the development of ion
 290 outflows and the temporal evolution between reconnection regimes.

291 The thermal energy conversion equation in collisionless plasma is

$$\frac{\partial U_s}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{H}_s + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_s = \left(\nabla \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{P}}_s \right) \cdot \mathbf{V}_s, \quad (5)$$

292 where $s = i, e$ denotes the particle species (ions and electrons). The thermal energy den-
 293 sity is defined as $U_s = \frac{1}{2}m_s \int (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_s)^2 f_s(\mathbf{v}) d\mathbf{v}$, where m_s is the particle mass, \mathbf{V}_s is
 294 the bulk velocity, and $f_s(\mathbf{v})$ is the velocity distribution function. The enthalpy flux is
 295 given by $\mathbf{H}_s = U_s \mathbf{V}_s + \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{P}}_s \cdot \mathbf{V}_s$, where $\overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{P}}_s$ is the pressure tensor. The heat flux is $\mathbf{q}_s =$
 296 $\frac{1}{2}m_s \int (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_s)^2 (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_s) f_s(\mathbf{v}) d\mathbf{v}$. To investigate the underlying mechanisms responsi-
 297 ble for the differences in ion heating between these two reconnection regimes, we exam-
 298 ine the terms in Eq. 5 for ions. To better interpret the ion heating process, we examine
 299 each term in the ion thermal energy equation, identifying their respective roles during
 300 electron-only and standard reconnection. Throughout this study, we use the local vari-
 301 ation of ion temperature ΔT_i to characterize ion heating, and interpret its underlying
 302 physics based on the temporal evolution of ion thermal energy described by the full Eu-
 303 lerian form of the ion thermal energy conversion equation (Eq. 5). To provide a more
 304 complete and quantitative analysis of ion heating, we have now computed all four terms
 305 in the ion thermal energy equation. To reduce the influence of numerical noise and bet-
 306 ter reflect the energy conversion, we integrated each term over a selected region in the
 307 reconnection outflow (as shown by the lime box in Figure 3). The results are presented
 308 in Figure 8. We normalize the integrated values by the corresponding ion temperature
 309 T_{i0} to better compare their relative contributions to heating. In Figure 8, the magnitude
 310 of each term is indicated at the end of each column, enabling a quantitative compari-
 311 son. At $t = 280\omega_{pi}^{-1}$, all four terms are negligible, consistent with the nearly unchanged
 312 ion temperature observed at that time. At $t = 2400\omega_{pi}^{-1}$, the pressure work term is posi-
 313 tive, indicating work done by the pressure tensor on the ions. The divergence of the en-
 314 thalpy flux is also positive, while that of the heat flux is negative. The net result is a pos-

Figure 6. The three terms on the RHS of Eq. 3 at two times are shown. The left column corresponds to the electron-only reconnection regime, while the right column matches the standard reconnection regime. The acceleration of ions is mainly attributed to the electric force, which is about one order higher than the Lorentz force term in both regimes. The contribution of ion pressure tensor term is negligible.

Figure 7. 1-dimensional cuts of each term on the RHS of equation 4 along the lower current sheet at $t = 2400\omega_{pi}^{-1}$, plotted alongside the total E_x .

Figure 8. The integration of four terms in the Equation 5 over the selected outflow region (the lime boxes in Figure 3 (b) and (d)) at two different times in the first simulation: the pressure work term $(\nabla \cdot \vec{\mathbf{P}}_i) \cdot \mathbf{V}_i$, the divergence of the ion enthalpy flux $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{H}_i$, the divergence of the ion heat flux $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_i$, and the time derivative of the ion internal energy $\partial U_i / \partial t$.

315 itive $\partial U_i / \partial t$, consistent with the observed ion temperature increase. These results elu-
 316 cidate the ion heating mechanisms observed during the standard reconnection phase.

317 3.3 Effects of ion temperature on the evolution

318 To investigate the effect of ion temperature on the evolution from electron-only to
 319 standard reconnection, we conduct a simulation with an increased ion temperature which
 320 corresponds to $\beta_i = 25.0$. This value is chosen to demonstrate the impact of ion tem-
 321 perature on the evolution dynamics, particularly regarding the ion response to changes
 322 in magnetic field topology.

323 The evolution of the electron outflow velocity of this simulation is shown in Fig-
 324 ure 9 and is found to be similar to that observed in the former case. Super-Alfvénic elec-
 325 tron outflows form rapidly following the onset of reconnection (Figure 9 (b)), and their
 326 magnitudes gradually decrease as reconnection proceeds. When the islands grow suffi-
 327 ciently large, the electron outflow velocity reaches the level of the upstream Alfvén speed
 328 (Figure 9 (c) and (d)). However, the ion velocity profile exhibits an obviously different
 329 evolution. As shown in Figure 10, no discernible ion outflows are observed throughout
 330 the simulation, even when the magnetic island size and downstream region length are
 331 comparable to those in the previous case. In other words, the absence of an ion response
 332 is not due to an insufficient simulation duration or to the reconnection site region be-
 333 ing too small.

334 The temperature variations of electrons and ions at $t = 280 \omega_{pi}^{-1}$ and $t = 2240 \omega_{pi}^{-1}$
 335 in this case are presented in Figure 11. The electron temperature profiles at these times
 336 remain similar to those observed in the previous case, indicating that significant elec-
 337 tron heating persists. However, the ion temperature does not exhibit any discernible vari-
 338 ations, providing further evidence of the negligible ion coupling to the reconnection pro-
 339 cess in this case. Consequently, we conclude that the temporal evolution from electron-
 340 only to standard reconnection does not occur in this simulation, and the reconnection
 341 remains within the electron-only regime throughout the evolution.

Figure 9. Evolution of the electron flow velocity along the x direction with $\beta_i = 25.0$, normalized by the upstream Alfvén speed, V_{ex}/V_A . The Alfvén speed is calculated using the asymptotic in-plane magnetic field, B_{x0} . Electron outflows are observed following the onset of reconnection. As reconnection progresses, the reconnection region elongates, and the electron outflow velocity gradually decreases. The solid black curves represent the magnetic field lines. All plots share a common colorbar, positioned on the right side of the figure.

Figure 10. Evolution of the ion flow velocity along the x direction with $\beta_i = 25.0$, normalized by the upstream Alfvén speed, V_{ix}/V_A . The Alfvén speed is calculated using the asymptotic in-plane magnetic field, B_{x0} . Ion outflows are absent or negligible throughout the simulation. The solid black curves represent the magnetic field lines. All plots share a common colorbar, positioned on the right side of the figure. The lime boxes in panels (b) and (d) indicate the regions used for spatial integration of the terms in Equation 5 for the second simulation at two different times; the corresponding integration results are presented in Figure 12.

342 We have also computed all four terms in the ion thermal energy equation in this
 343 case: the pressure work term $\left(\nabla \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{P}}_i\right) \cdot \mathbf{V}_i$, the divergence of the ion enthalpy flux $\nabla \cdot$
 344 \mathbf{H}_i , the divergence of the ion heat flux $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_i$, and the time derivative of the ion inter-
 345 nal energy $\partial U_i / \partial t$. As we did in the first simulation, we integrated each term over a se-
 346 lected region in the reconnection outflow (as shown by the lime box in Figure 10) and
 347 normalized the integrated values by the corresponding ion temperature T_{i0} in this case.
 348 The spatial integration is performed over regions with equal areas for both cases at $t =$
 349 $280\omega_{pi}^{-1}$. For the second comparison ($t = 2400\omega_{pi}^{-1}$ in the first simulation and $t = 2240\omega_{pi}^{-1}$
 350 in the second simulation), we also ensure identical integration areas. In the second sim-
 351 ulation, as shown in Figure 12 (note the different vertical axis range from Figure 8), all
 352 four terms remain small at both time slices, significantly smaller than the values in the
 353 first simulation at $t = 2400\omega_{pi}^{-1}$. As shown in the Figure 12, the value of $\partial U_i / \partial t$ itself
 354 is significantly smaller than the values of standard reconnection phase in the lower- β_i
 355 case (Figure 8). This confirms that the net temporal variation of ion internal energy is
 356 negligible in the high- β_i simulation, which is consistent with the absence of noticeable
 357 ion temperature increase (ΔT_i) in this case. This can also be understood from the def-
 358 inition of ion thermal energy and its derivative:

$$\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{2} m_i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_i)^2 f_i(\mathbf{v}) d\mathbf{v}.$$

359 Here, U_i represents the second moment of the ion velocity distribution relative to the
 360 bulk flow velocity \mathbf{V}_i , and its time variation depends on how both the distribution width
 361 and the bulk flow evolve. In our large- β_i simulation, ions typically have large thermal
 362 speeds, resulting in a large gyroradius ρ_i . Due to the presence of a finite guide field and
 363 the small transverse scale of the reconnection region, the ions are weakly coupled to the
 364 localized reconnection electric field structures. They experience little acceleration or heat-
 365 ing from the reconnection process. As a result, neither the bulk ion flow velocity \mathbf{V}_i nor
 366 the thermal spread of the distribution function changes significantly in time. Consequently,
 367 the ion internal energy exhibits negligible variation over time, and $\partial U_i / \partial t$ stays tiny, con-
 368 sistent with what is observed in our high- β_i simulation.

369 4 Conclusions and Discussion

370 The spontaneous evolution from electron-only to standard ion-coupled magnetic
 371 reconnection in the presence of guide fields is investigated via 2.5-dimensional PIC sim-
 372 ulations. The key findings of this work can be summarized as follows:

- 373 • Spontaneous transition from electron-only to standard reconnection is observed
 374 in moderate $\beta_i (= 2.56)$ simulations. Initially, only electrons exhibit obvious out-
 375 flows and heating, while ion response is negligible. As reconnection progresses and
 376 magnetic islands grow, ion acceleration and heating become prominent, signaling
 377 the enhancement of ion coupling.
- 378 • Ion acceleration is primarily driven by the in-plane Hall electric field (E_x). As the
 379 simulation proceeds, there is more space for ions to be accelerated.
- 380 • Ion heating during the reconnection evolution is analyzed. With increasing ion cou-
 381 pling, both the work done by the ion pressure gradient and the enthalpy flux are
 382 identified as the primary contributors to ion heating.
- 383 • The evolution from electron-only to standard reconnection is suppressed when the
 384 ion gyroradius is comparable to or exceeds the system size ($\rho_i \gtrsim L$). In our high-
 385 β_i simulation, ions remain demagnetized and do not couple to the reconnection
 386 process, resulting in persistent electron-only behavior.

387 Specifically, our simulation of $\beta_i = 2.56$ illustrates the spontaneous evolution from
 388 electron-only to standard reconnection. In the initial phase, electrons rapidly respond

Figure 11. The electron and ion temperature variations at two times are shown with $\beta_i = 25.0$. Here $\Delta T_s = (T_s(t = t_1)/T_s(t = 0)) - 1$. The results show the reconnection stays in the electron-only regime throughout the simulation. Figures within the same row share a common colorbar, which is positioned on the right side of the corresponding row.

Figure 12. The integration of four terms in the Equation 5 over the selected outflow region (the lime boxes in Figure 10 (b) and (d)) at two different times in the second simulation: the pressure work term $(\nabla \cdot \vec{\mathbf{P}}_i) \cdot \mathbf{V}_i$, the divergence of the ion enthalpy flux $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{H}_i$, the divergence of the ion heat flux $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_i$, and the time derivative of the ion internal energy $\partial U_i / \partial t$.

389 to changes in the magnetic field topology, with observable electron outflows and electron
 390 heating, while the ion response remains either minimal or entirely absent. These results
 391 are consistent with the characteristics of electron-only reconnection. As reconnection pro-
 392 gresses, magnetic islands grow larger, and the downstream region elongates, providing
 393 time and space for ions to be accelerated and heated. Consequently, the extent of ion
 394 coupling to the reconnection process increases, signifying the evolution toward the stan-
 395 dard reconnection regime. At this stage, both ion outflows and ion heating become promi-
 396 nent. Our analysis indicates that the Hall electric field serves as the primary driver of
 397 ion acceleration during this evolution. As ion velocity increases, the work done by the
 398 ion pressure gradient term intensifies, and the ion enthalpy flux becomes more pronounced,
 399 both contributing to ion heating.

400 We further investigate the impact of ion temperature on this temporal evolution
 401 by conducting a simulation with high ion temperature, resulting in a large ion plasma
 402 β_i . While the electron response remains similar to the previous case, we observe a re-
 403 markable difference in the ion response. Specifically, neither ion outflows nor ion heat-
 404 ing are observed, indicating that the system remains in the electron-only reconnection
 405 regime throughout the simulation. A higher ion temperature leads to a larger ion gy-
 406 roradius, causing ions to decouple from the magnetic reconnection dynamics and lose mag-
 407 netization. Consequently, the ions are not effectively accelerated or heated by the recon-
 408 nection process. Recently, Fan et al. (2025) further proposed that in high- β_i regimes, the
 409 suppression of bulk ion outflows may be related to the behavior of high-energy ions, which
 410 experience different acceleration patterns. While our simulations do not distinguish be-
 411 tween ion energy populations, our finding of weak ion coupling at high β_i is qualitatively
 412 consistent with their conclusion.

413 Although previous studies have explored the differences and transitions between
 414 electron-only reconnection and standard reconnection, the exact relationship and bound-
 415 aries between them remain not fully understood. Previous simulations have demonstrated
 416 that the reconnection regime is governed by the ratio between simulation box size L and
 417 ion inertial length d_i or the ratio between L and ion gyroradius ρ_i (Sharma Pyakurel et
 418 al., 2019; Guan et al., 2023). Specifically, when the ratio L/ρ_i is small, reconnection re-
 419 sides in the electron-only regime, whereas when L/ρ_i reaches the order of tens, recon-
 420 nection transitions to the traditional ion-coupled regime (Guan et al., 2023). Guan et
 421 al. (2024) proposed that this criterion primarily applies to reconnection under guide fields.
 422 For the anti-parallel configuration, they pointed out that it is the ratio L/λ_i , where λ_i
 423 is the ion meandering motion scale, that governs the ion response. Simulations and ob-
 424 servations further indicate that electron-only reconnection can serve as an intermediary
 425 between a quiet current sheet and standard reconnection (S. Lu, Wang, et al., 2020; S. Lu
 426 et al., 2022; Hubbert et al., 2022). However, these studies utilized externally driven re-
 427 connection in their simulations. This raises the question of whether electron-only recon-
 428 nection can play a similar transitional role in spontaneous reconnection processes. Re-
 429 cently, Guan et al. (2025) investigated this problem in the anti-parallel reconnection case
 430 and discussed the roles of electrons, ions, and B_y pileup (here y is the direction verti-
 431 cal to the current sheet) in this evolution. In the present study, we address this ques-
 432 tion in the presence of guide fields and study the temporal evolution between these two
 433 regimes under different ion temperatures. We note that, in contrast to previous stud-
 434 ies based on parameter scans (Sharma Pyakurel et al., 2019; Guan et al., 2023), the present
 435 work focuses on the temporal evolution of magnetic reconnection dynamics within a sin-
 436 gle system, and on how this evolution is influenced by the ion temperature.

437 Our first simulation focuses on how a single run evolves from electron-only to ion-
 438 coupled reconnection over time, and the second case is used to explore how increased ion
 439 temperature affects this evolution. The results of our second case are indeed in agree-
 440 ment with the findings of Guan et al. (2023), where the ratio $(L/2)/\rho_i \approx 3.54$ (with
 441 L divided by 2 due to the presence of two current sheets in our simulation box) was in-

442 sufficient to trigger ion coupling, while our results extend the applicability of their find-
 443 ings to the reconnection simulation within a larger box. Although our findings share some
 444 consistency with those reported by Guan et al. (2023) (which also suggests the robust-
 445 ness of our results), there are notable differences. Specifically, our study is conducted within
 446 the context of different environments, characterized by a much longer current sheet. Fur-
 447 thermore, our first simulation with low ion β_i captures the temporal evolution from electron-
 448 only reconnection to standard reconnection, a phenomenon not observed in their sim-
 449 ulations. When the ion β_i is sufficiently high (with a larger thermal velocity and a big-
 450 ger gyroradius ρ_i), the ratio $(L/2)/\rho_i$ decreases, indicating that ions lack the space nec-
 451 essary for effective remagnetization, thereby inhibiting this evolution.

452 The findings on ion acceleration in our study are largely consistent with those from
 453 electron-dominated current sheet reconnection simulations (Guan et al., 2024); however,
 454 notable differences are also observed. In our simulations, the ion pressure gradient force
 455 (from the momentum equation) is negligible, whereas in Guan et al. (2024), it was shown
 456 to play a decelerating role in ion acceleration. Additionally, in electron-dominated cur-
 457 rent sheet simulations without guide fields (Guan et al., 2024), the three terms exhibit
 458 a symmetric structure. In contrast, this symmetry is not preserved in our simulations
 459 due to the influence of the guide field (Birn & Priest, 2007). This asymmetry, induced
 460 by the guide field, is consistent with that reported in previous guide-field reconnection
 461 studies (e.g., Sharma Pyakurel et al. (2019)). Recently, Payne et al. (2024) proposed the
 462 Hall electric field structures in the exhaust act as a means of energy exchange between
 463 energized electrons and cold ions, particularly during the rapid growth phase of recon-
 464 nection. In our simulations, we observe clear signatures of ion acceleration and heating
 465 during the late stage of reconnection (i.e., the transition to standard reconnection), which
 466 is consistent with their interpretation. From this perspective, their analysis offers ad-
 467 ditional physical insight into our findings.

468 In this work, we employed a force-free current sheet equilibrium, a characteristic
 469 configuration commonly found in the magnetosheath. Our findings indicate that stan-
 470 dard reconnection can evolve from electron-only reconnection. Given that multiple electron-
 471 only reconnection events have been observed in the magnetosheath (Phan et al., 2018;
 472 Payne et al., 2025), our results provide useful insights into the role of electron-only re-
 473 connection in the magnetosheath environments. Recently, it has been verified in obser-
 474 vations that the reconnection rate in electron-only reconnection events is not steady (Tian
 475 et al., 2025), which is also consistent with previous simulation studies (Guan et al., 2024;
 476 Ren et al., 2025). Moreover, the rate is usually found to be larger than 0.1 during the
 477 electron-only reconnection stage (Sharma Pyakurel et al., 2019; Guan et al., 2024; Ren
 478 et al., 2025; Fan et al., 2025). Our results align with these findings; however, after evol-
 479 ving to the standard reconnection stage, the reconnection rate reaches a steady state and
 480 remains at approximately 0.1, as there is still adequate magnetic flux in the upstream
 481 region when our simulation stops. In addition, similar to the results of Barbhuiya et
 482 al. (2025), our simulations exhibit a temporal evolution that progresses from the onset
 483 phase to the growth phase and ultimately to a steady state, during which we also ob-
 484 serve the progressive opening of the reconnection separatrices.

485 Additionally, we think that the ion-to-electron mass ratio may impact the recon-
 486 nection temporal evolution, making it a potential direction for future research (here we
 487 use $m_i/m_e = 100$). Although the ion mass in our simulations is fixed to unity, the dif-
 488 ferent mass ratios and varied electron mass may still play a role in this process, as ion
 489 acceleration is primarily driven by the Hall electric field. A larger mass ratio, with lighter
 490 electrons, could result in a faster electron response to changes in magnetic field topol-
 491 ogy, thereby altering the electric field structure and affecting ion dynamics. Guide field
 492 strength is another factor that may influence this temporal evolution, as it governs the
 493 scale of electron and ion motion in guide-field reconnection. In the present study, the guide
 494 field strength is fixed at $B_g/B_{x0} = 1$. With stronger guide fields, the ion gyro-radius

495 becomes smaller, making it easier for ions to remain or become magnetized. As a result,
 496 the evolution from electron-only to standard reconnection is also expected to be altered.
 497 Both the effects of the mass ratio and guide field strength warrant further investigation
 498 in future studies. To further generalize our findings, we plan to investigate this problem
 499 under different initial equilibria (such as the Harris current sheet) in a follow-up study.
 500 Most electron-only reconnection simulations conducted thus far have been 2.5-dimensional,
 501 under the assumption of invariance along the out-of-plane direction (i.e., $\partial/\partial z = 0$).
 502 However, in realistic physical systems, magnetic reconnection is inherently 3-dimensional,
 503 with non-negligible variations along the third dimension (P. Pyakurel et al., 2021). There-
 504 fore, it is plausible to extend these investigations to 3-dimensional simulations, which
 505 we leave as the focus of future work. The triggering mechanism of reconnection in the
 506 present configuration remains another intriguing topic. The initial force-free equilibrium
 507 contains a strong electron velocity shear, which may give rise to an electron Kelvin–Helmholtz
 508 (electron-KH) instability (Fermo et al., 2012). The presence of vortex-like structures within
 509 the magnetic islands observed in our simulations is suggestive of this possibility. We have
 510 calculated the growth rates of both the electron-KH instability and the collisionless tear-
 511 ing mode instability (Fermo et al., 2012; Drake & Lee, 1977; Pritchett et al., 1991), and
 512 the results demonstrate that the growth rate of the electron-KH instability significantly
 513 exceeds that of the collisionless tearing mode under our simulation conditions (see Ap-
 514 pendix A). This indicates that the observed magnetic reconnection is most likely initi-
 515 ated and dominated by the electron-KH instability. Recently, Yoon et al. (2024) showed
 516 that high plasma β can inhibit current sheets from pinching down to kinetic scales, thereby
 517 suppressing the onset of collisionless reconnection. Their findings provides more insights
 518 for understanding the absence of ion coupling observed in our high- β cases and this con-
 519 nection warrants further investigation.

520 Appendix A Evolution of the full simulation domain and Growth rate 521 calculation

522 The snapshots of the full simulation domain at $t = 500, 1000,$ and $2400\omega_{pi}^{-1}$ (for
 523 the first simulation) or $2240\omega_{pi}^{-1}$ (for the second simulation) are shown in Figure A1 and
 524 Figure A2 for two simulations, respectively. These plots confirm that the two current sheets
 525 remain spatially separated by at least $\sim 8d_i$ throughout the simulation, and no signif-
 526 icant interactions are observed.

527 To estimate the potential influence of periodic boundaries, we calculate the char-
 528 acteristic recirculation time using the outflow speed $V_{\text{out}} \approx 1.6v_A = 0.0128c$ as fol-
 529 lows

$$t_{\text{recirc}} = \frac{L_x}{V_{\text{out}}} \approx 1950\omega_{pi}^{-1}, \quad (\text{A1})$$

530 where L_x is the length of the simulation box in the outflow (x) direction, and V_{out} is the
 531 characteristic outflow velocity of the plasma. In this estimate, we take $V_{\text{out}} \approx 1.6v_A$,
 532 where $v_A = B/\sqrt{\mu_0 n_i m_i}$ is the Alfvén speed based on the upstream magnetic field strength.
 533 ω_{pi}^{-1} is the inverse of the ion plasma frequency with $\omega_{pi} = \sqrt{n_i e^2/\varepsilon_0 m_i}$. c is the speed
 534 of light. Since our simulation extends to $t = 2400\omega_{pi}^{-1}$, some recirculation may occur
 535 near the end of the run. However, as demonstrated by Fujimoto (2006), simulations with
 536 smaller box sizes may exhibit a slight delay in the onset of reconnection, but the sub-
 537 sequent evolution remains similar to that in larger systems. We also emphasize that the
 538 main focus of our study is on the temporal evolution from electron-only to standard re-
 539 connection. This process occurs predominantly in the early phase ($t < 1200\omega_{pi}^{-1}$), well
 540 before the recirculation time is reached. During this phase, the reconnection character-
 541 istics are clearly dominated by electron-only dynamics and unaffected by boundary ef-
 542 fects. At later times, when the system transitions into the standard reconnection regime,
 543 the insensitivity to box size reported by Fujimoto (2006) becomes applicable.

Figure A1. Snapshots of the full simulation domain at $t = 500, 1000,$ and $2400 \omega_{pi}^{-1}$ in the first simulation.

Figure A2. Snapshots of the full simulation domain at $t = 500, 1000,$ and $2240 \omega_{pi}^{-1}$ in the second simulation.

544 To further clarify the triggering mechanism of magnetic reconnection in our sim-
 545 ulations, we have quantitatively compared the growth rates of the electron-KH instabil-
 546 ity γ_{KH} and the collisionless tearing mode instability γ_{TM} (Fermo et al., 2012; Drake &
 547 Lee, 1977; Pritchett et al., 1991). The growth rates are calculated as follows:

$$\gamma_{\text{KH}} \simeq \frac{\Delta V_{ex}}{d_e}, \quad (\text{A2})$$

$$\gamma_{\text{TM}} \simeq \frac{(k v_{\text{the}} c^2 / (\sqrt{\pi} \omega_{pe}^2 \lambda^2)) (2 + k\lambda)(1 - k\lambda)}{1 + 2\rho_e^2 / \lambda^2}, \quad (\text{A3})$$

548 where v_{the} is the electron thermal velocity, $\rho_e = v_{\text{the}} / \Omega_{ce}$ is the electron Larmor
 549 radius, λ is the half-thickness of the current sheet, k is the wavenumber along the cur-
 550 rent sheet, ΔV_{ex} is the jump in electron flow velocity across the current sheet, ω_{pe} is the
 551 electron plasma frequency, and $d_e = c / \omega_{pe}$ is the electron inertial length.

552 For the tearing mode, we adopt the maximum growth rate at $k\lambda = 0.55$, as dis-
 553 cussed by Pritchett et al. (1991). Using our simulation parameters, the ratio of these growth
 554 rates is found to be

$$\frac{\gamma_{\text{KH}}}{\gamma_{\text{TM}}} \approx 6.8 > 1 \quad (\text{A4})$$

555 This quantitative comparison clearly demonstrates that the electron-KH instability growth
 556 rate exceeds that of the collisionless tearing mode instability. Besides, Z. Wang et al. (1992)
 557 pointed out that when the plasma thermal speed is much larger than the flow speed, and
 558 the flow speed exceeds the Alfvén speed—as is the case in our simulations—the growth
 559 rate of the electron-KH instability can be enhanced. These results support electron-KH
 560 as the dominant mechanism responsible for the onset and early development of recon-
 561 nection in our simulations.

562 Open Research Section

563 The data supporting the findings of this study are available at Ren (2025).

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